

PREVALENCE AND TRENDS OF INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE IN UYO URBAN, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is one of the most prevalent social problems in Uyo Urban, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria as cases continue to rise very rapidly in the area. This study therefore was to ascertain the prevalence and the trends of intimate partner violence that can give rise to deviant sexual acts. It adopted the anomie theory which assumes that deviant behaviour arises in situations where there is a breakdown of law and order. Participants in the study were purposively drawn using a snowball sampling technique while data were obtained through interviews of participants and key informants. Data analysis was done qualitatively as participant responses were grouped in themes according to the study specific objectives. Results indicated that intimate partner violence contributes to deviant sexual acts in the study area. It was also found that the most dominant form of IPV in the area is physical abuse (punching, slapping, and shoving) and married women were the most abused set of people in the study area. Allegations of infidelity and economic factors were found to be the major drivers of IPV and sexual deviations were coping measures for IPV. To address the high prevalence of IPV, punishments of offenders by the law should be enforced to serve as deterrence to others and also encourage “silent victims” to speak up and call for help.

Keywords: Intimate Partner Violence, Deviant behaviour, Sexual deviant acts, and Sexual Violence

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt to the fact that we are living in interesting times of the 21st century. The world is changing and the impact of these social changes is enormous and far-reaching

and contradictory to what was obtained in the past. For instance, social norms, laws, values, customs and cultures are fast changing from one society to another and the reality they produce is that what was unacceptable yesterday has in some cases become acceptable and legitimate. Violence is not new to many people and societies. History is dotted with many records and forms of violence, including Intimate partner violence (IPV). According to Encyclopedia Britannica, Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) refers to behaviour within an intimate relationship that causes physical, sexual or psychological harm, including acts of aggression, sexual coercion, psychological abuse, and controlling behaviours. IPV could be measured as Physical Violence, Sexual Violence and Emotional Violence. Contrary to popular belief, physical abuse in relationships is a serious and widespread problem. It is also tragic and drastically changes lives.

The fact that it occurs in silence, between couples in intimate relationships, it is imperceptible to the outer world until it is too late to do anything about it (Effah-Chukwuma, Ukommi and Bassey, 2019). Although physical abuse is the most obvious type, it rarely occurs in a relationship when there isn't verbal or emotional abuse present. However, a relationship can turn into a living nightmare when physical violence is added to mental abuse and insults. Physical violence is not just about battery, there are other forms of physical abuse in relationships besides beatings. Physical violence also involves (i) Pushing, shaking or throwing something at the partner (ii) slapping him or her, twisting the arm, pulling the hair, kicking, dragging, beating, punching or hitting the partner with something harmful (iii) choking or burning a partner on purpose, threatening or attacking a partner with a weapon for instance gun or knife. Contrary to popular belief, physical abuse in relationships is a serious and widespread problem. It is also tragic and drastically changes lives. Sexual violence on the other hand is forced sexual intercourse- physically forcing a partner to perform any other sexual act when undesired and forcing her with threats to perform sexual acts without her consent. It is any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act by violence or coercion act to traffic a person, or act directed against a person's sexuality, regardless of the relationship to the victim. It occurs in times of peace and armed conflict situations, it is widespread and is considered to be one of the most traumatic, pervasive, and most common human rights violations.

Sexual violence is a serious public health problem and has a profound short or long-term impact on physical and mental health (Effah-Chukwuma, Ukommi and Bassey, 2022). The last one would be emotional violence, which entails humiliating the partner in public, threatening to hurt or harm someone close to the partner's family and finally insulting or making the partner feel bad about themselves. Since the beginning of time, countless individuals have endured unimaginable suffering in violent Intimate Partner relationships, especially in marriages. Many of them have stayed in these unions out of fear of being labelled as marital failures. Some do it for their kids' sake, while others do it because they do not believe in divorce or the lack of finances to move on. However, the scope of intimate partner violence has moved beyond violence against women in a romantic relationship to also cover violence against men in intimate relationships although this is a rare occurrence (Coker, Davis, Arias and Brandt, 2002). Even though there has been so much alarm about intimate partner violence against women across the globe, intimate partner violence against men is a reality. It occurs virtually in every society to varying degrees. The problem in conducting studies that seek to describe violence in terms of gender is the amount of silence, fear and shame that results from abuse within families and relationships. This is why domestic

violence against men remains largely unreported (Abayomi, 2014).

Nigerian society is a highly patriarchal one, in which men have bloated egos and high self-esteem (Brown and Akpan, 2020). Though there is a prevalence of intimate partner violence against women in Nigeria as many women have died, brutalized or maimed for life by their violent male counterparts, however, there is also a prevalence of domestic violence against men, which has largely remained under-reported. The under-reporting of intimate partner violence according to Abayomi, (2014) is almost universal and may be due to the sensitive nature of the subject. Husband punching, slapping, kicking, nail scratching, sex deprivation and killing are realities that occur in Nigeria. The tragedy is that men who find themselves in this situation hide and do not talk openly about their ugly experiences, as talking about it will bruise their egos and expose them to ridicule in a male-dominated society. Brown and Akpan (2020) also found that familism and conformity to family loyalty, trust, integrity, unity, progress and defence of family values have induced an expansion on the spaces of crime and in some cases, result to homicide and intimate partner violence.

Several laws protect, men and women alike, and things have changed. We now live in a time where violence against a partner in an intimate relationship is considered a serious crime. Despite all the efforts and sensitization programs carried out by the different government parastatals, NGOs and human rights bodies, there are still cases of violence against women in intimate partner relationships. Intimate partner violence has been identified among some couples in Uyo municipality. Cases abound whereby some husbands maltreat their spouses, causing some of them to leave their marriages. Thereafter they might decide to remain unmarried and subsequently engage in sexual deviations such as masturbation, lesbianism, and prostitution to mention but a few while some may stay back in such relationships and engage in extramarital affairs, masturbation and bisexuality.

Sexual deviation, otherwise known as Paraphilia or sexual perversion is the experience of intense sexual arousal to atypical objects, situations, fantasies, behaviours or individuals. It has also been defined as sexual interest in anything other than a consenting human partner. It presents in the form of lesbianism, masturbation, prostitution, and total abstinence from sexual activities to mention but a few. While it has been frequently suggested that sexual deviations are learned, the learning has usually been thought of as taking place during one traumatic experience.

Thompson (2016) explains how victims who have experienced IPV (especially in marriages) tend to indulge in sexual activities/sexual self-gratification that can be termed sexual deviation in a bid to ease themselves and survive. Examples of such sexual deviations include incest, homosexuality, lesbianism, bisexuality, trans-sexualism, masturbation and extramarital affairs just to mention a few. Jamali (2016), found that the frequency of domestic violence can increase the risk of sexual dysfunction.

Globally, 27% of ever-partnered women aged 15-49 years are estimated to have experienced physical, sexual, or both, intimate partner violence in their lifetime, with 13% (10-16%) experiencing it in the past year before they were surveyed (Global, regional and national prevalence estimates of physical or sexual or both intimate partner violence against women in 2018 published February 16, 2022).

In Africa and Nigeria where culture exerts enormous influence that seems to affect women negatively, the rate of Intimate Partners Violence expectedly is alarmingly high. It is put at 36% (CDC, 2016). This is more than the global average. Considering the scanty nature of comprehensive statistics on IPV in Nigeria, one is left to his/her guesses. According to the data gathered by UNICEF on violent unions published on May 2022, in nearly half of 67

countries with available data, more than 1 in 5 ever-married adolescent girls have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by a husband or partner within the past year. These include countries spanning regions from Asia to sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean, indicating that adolescent girls everywhere are exposed to this form of violence.

Akwa Ibom State is not left out as there have been cases of IPV between couples in intimate relationships in Uyo urban. According to a publication on business day dated 22nd of February 2022, a pastor in Eket, Akwa Ibom State reportedly killed his wife and buried her in a shallow grave in their rented apartment but was later apprehended by the police for the alleged murder of his wife. Another incident was reported to have happened in Ikot Ataku, Okon in Eket Local Government Area involved one Pastor Chris Enoch, the founder of Omega Word Global Ministries, Enoch who has five children from his wife, Patience, he allegedly killed, hails from Ebonyi State. These are evidences that there are indeed cases of IPV in Uyo Urban. Bomomi *et al.* (2017) stressed through their findings that SD was a direct cause of Intimate Partner Violence without taking into consideration that IPV can equally lead to SD.

Since a woman's life is fundamentally shaped by her sexuality and a woman's sexuality can be affected by a variety of things, including medical diseases, social-religious views, age, psychological problems, despair, mental stress, disbelief and an unfulfilling marriage, and verbal and physical abuse, violence against women can lead to the development of psychological diseases such as melancholy, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, phobias and panic attacks (Kassel, 2021). These issues can negatively impact the sexual functions, connection, orientation and options of couples. Thus, this research becomes necessary to find out the prevalence and trends of intimate partner violence within Uyo metropolis.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Anomie Theory

Anomie is a social condition defined by an uprooting or breakdown of any moral values, standards or guidance for individuals to follow. Anomie is believed to possibly evolve from a conflict of belief system and causes the breakdown of social bonds between an individual and the community (both economic and primary socialization). An example is alienation in a person that can progress into a dysfunctional inability to integrate within normative situations of their social world such as finding a job, achieving success in relationships, etc. The term, commonly understood to mean normlessness, is believed to have been popularized by French sociologist, Emile Durkheim in his influential book *Suicide* (1897). Durkheim described anomie as "derangement," and "an insatiable will. He used the term to explain that desire without limit can never be fulfilled; it only becomes more intense. For Durkheim, anomie arises more generally from a mismatch between personal or group standards and wider social standards; or from the lack of a social, which produces moral deregulation and an absence of legitimate aspirations.

Applying this theory to the study, therefore, victims of intimate partner violence may have adopted other forms of sexual pleasure like extramarital affairs, masturbation and bisexuality as a soothing strategy for their sexual satisfaction which may obviously be an aberration from the normal conventions of society in terms of its expectations on sexual intercourse. The ugly experiences of violence by the victim have now constituted the anomie on which, the victim breaks away from social conventions to attain sexual satisfaction

through socially unexpected channels. In the study area, this theory will be either refuted or justified when the fieldwork is completed.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research method was adopted for this study. Survey research is the process of conducting research using a selected or defined population (Visser, Krosnick and Lavrakas, 2000). The area of this study was Uyo Urban. Participants in the study were drawn within the geographical boundaries of Uyo Urban area. Uyo Urban constitutes areas covering Uyo Local Government and major areas like Aka Road, Nwaniba, Ewet Housing Estate, Abak Road, Barracks Road, Ikot Ekpene Road, Oron Road and the University of Uyo Town Campus Area. Uyo Urban boast of several infrastructural facilities like Ibom Tropicana, and the E-library, The population of this study constituted mainly women above the age of 18 who had experienced at least one form of intimate partner violence either from their previous or current intimate relationship. However, two men were utilized as key informants to enable the researcher to elicit the necessary data from the point of view of gender consciousness. The sample of this study was 120 respondents (115 participants and 5 key informants). This was attained through a maturation process where the researchers gathered data from as many participants as possible until the responses reached a saturation point. The sampling technique of this study was based on non-probability sampling methods. The purposive and snowball sampling techniques were adopted in the selection of participants for the study. While the purposive sampling technique was used in recruiting key informants, a combination of the snowball and purposive sampling techniques was used in recruiting participants for in-depth interviews and focus group discussions respectively.

The purposive sampling was adopted for this study. It is a non-probability sampling technique in which the sampling members are chosen only based on the researcher's knowledge and judgment. As the researcher's knowledge is instrumental and primary in this sampling process, there is a chance that the results will be lightly accurate with minimal error. This was chosen because the researcher intentionally went for those members in the study area who have experienced any form of IPV.

In addition, the snowball sampling was also adopted in the study. It is a non-probability sampling technique in which the samples provide referrals to recruit other samples required for a research study. This sampling technique can go on and on just as the snowball increases in size, in this case, the sample size, till when the researcher has enough data to analyse and draw conclusions. In this study, the Human Rights Commission, the Directorate of Social Welfare, as well as Brighter Hope Initiative, were consulted for information relating to intimate partner violence and its victims in Uyo Urban. Through these organizations, contacts were established with victims of intimate partner violence and interview sessions and FGDs took place.

Data were obtained from 95 participants in an in-depth interview and a group of 20 members who were involved in a focused group discussion. Furthermore, 5 key informants were interviewed in a key informant interview as well. Primary data were obtained with the help of seven research/field assistants in 22 days. The interview guide was used as one of the instruments for eliciting data from participants via in-depth interviews, key informant interviews and focused group discussions. In addition, oral interviews were applied in many cases to further buttress the content of the interview guide. Data collected for this study were analyzed qualitatively. However, data related to the personal characteristics of respondents

like age, marital status and educational qualification were presented using the simple percentage (%). Collected data related to the objectives of the study therefore were analyzed qualitatively and grouped in themes in line with the study's specific objectives. In this analysis, similar and dissimilar responses were grouped under specific headings to show divergent opinions on the subject.

RESULT

On the forms of intimate partner violence experienced, the following responses were given:

“Most times, he slaps me; that one is very often. But on very few occasions, he punches me. Sexually, that one happened only once (31 years old; female; businesswoman).

Another participant adds this variant view:

“My husband is so used to punching me whenever we have an argument or a fight. I have left the house about four times because of this. I have also been hospitalized two times due to his abusive blows in my stomach” (28-year-old married woman; civil servant).

Another participant contributes as follows:

“Slapping. He slaps me most of the times that he abuses me. Although if he gets hotter, it can move to pushing and/or punching” (34-year-old farmer; female).

What forms of IPV are prevalent in Uyo where you domicile? “

One of the most prevalent forms of IPV complaints is physical battery followed by sexual abuse (rape) (BHI, Uyo).

One of our key informants has thus:

“Mostly are rape and other forms of physical battery like slapping, punching, hitting and others. Those are the most notable cases in Uyo. (Human Rights Commission, Uyo)

What form of help do you give the supposed victims and how can you assess the effects of such assistance?

“We take action; ranging from counselling and ADR methods to legal actions and in some extreme cases, we encourage the victim to initiate an arrest on the perpetrator. These moves, depending on the magnitude of violence, usually prove effective. In some cases, the victims seek redress while the perpetrator signs an undertaking never to initiate IPV again” (Human Rights Commission, Uyo).

One of our key informants shares the following:

“Here in our NGO, we support female victims of IPV to file an

official case with the HRC and even the police to seek redress. For those who are too economically dependent, we ensure that we set them up with a business and strongly encourage them to be self-reliant and by so doing, it reduces the prevalence of IPV? (BHI, Uyo).

Another key informant contributes thus:

“When the violence is too serious and recurrent like serious battery and rape (for single), we initiate an arrest and encourage the victim to file a suit to prosecute the alleged perpetrator. Although some of them do not, but a few do. We get the abusers to sign an undertaking and also pay damages to the victims. In most of these instances, the results are always okay” (Social Welfare, Women Development Centre, Uyo).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study has established that intimate partner violence is prevalent in Uyo Urban and this is usually manifested in the form of physical battery like punching, pushing/shoving, slapping and head butting. In addition, several forms of sexual abuse have been found to also abound in Uyo metropolis such as marital rape as well as sexual assault among non-married partners.

As a coping mechanism, therefore, these manifested expressions of intimate partner violence mostly suffered by women have gradually resulted in some forms of sexual deviation as found in the study area. Although these sexual acts are socially proscribed by the vast majority of residents in the study area, these supposed victims engage in them as a coping mechanism for IPV they suffer in their intimate relationships. These findings are largely in contravention of the popular opinion that sexual deviations trigger intimate partner violence. In this case, the study has shown that there exists a plethora of sexual deviant involvements (extra-marital affairs, masturbation and bi-sexuality) that are caused by intimate partner violence. This study shows that most practitioners of these sexually deviant acts do so as a way to achieve sexual desires which have largely been bashed due to a recurrence of violent attacks by their intimate partner.

It was found that the prevalence of IPV in the study area stands at an average of 4-5 officially reported cases in the study area monthly and about an average of 60 officially recorded cases yearly for the past five years and this is alarmingly very disturbing. This is however comparatively low in comparison with the findings of Coston (2021) who submitted that the prevalence of IPV in Massachusetts stands at an average of 9 cases monthly and over 500 officially recorded IPV cases in the past five years.

CONCLUSION

This study has brought to the fore that intimate partner violence can trigger deviant sexual acts like extramarital sex, masturbation and bisexuality. The study clearly showed that the consequence of IPV cuts beyond physical and emotional consequences and penetrates sexual deviant behaviours. The study also established that physical and verbal abuses are the most perpetrated form of IPV perpetrated in the study area even as most of these violent acts occur at home where both partners dwell.

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